

Conference Abstract

Considering air quality in the long-term ecological monitoring of the Spanish National Parks network

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Abstract

The Mediterranean Basin is recognized as a Biodiversity Hotspot for conservation priorities, mainly due to the high biodiversity of plants. Different environmental protection categories of the territory can help to ensure the long-term preservation of biodiversity and habitats. Among them, National Park is the legal category providing the highest protection for nature areas with remarkable ecological and cultural value. These areas represent valuable locations for long-term monitoring of ecological conservation and ecosystem functioning.

The Spanish National Parks Network comprises 16 natural areas, including mountain ranges, volcanic habitats, different types of forest, scrublands and grasslands, and aquatic and marine ecosystems. All the National Parks are part of the European Natura 2000 network. Moreover, 6 of them are part of the LTER-Spain network. By law, National Parks must include a long-term Monitoring and Evaluation Plan for the Network, including

ecological, sociological, and functional monitoring programmes. Within the ecological monitoring programme, besides flora, fauna and ecosystem functioning assessments, climate is also considered as one of the main drivers of global change. Tree crown condition is assessed in all the parks with forests following the methodology of ICP-Forest Level I. The next step is to include air quality, since atmospheric pollution is another important driver of global change that can affect ecosystem health and functioning. Particularly tropospheric ozone and atmospheric nitrogen deposition are expected to be exceeding the limit values for vegetation protection.

Air quality monitoring networks are mainly focused on the protection of human health, thus some very valuable areas for biodiversity might not be represented by air monitoring stations. In addition, atmospheric deposition is not included at the air quality monitoring stations. Moreover, the extension of some of the National Parks, the complex orography and the different climate, morphology and air pollution sources that influence the National Parks, represent a challenge for managers to design an air quality monitoring program with an efficient use of resources. To address this challenge and provide the information needed to design an air quality network in National Parks, a new project is being developed combining local monitoring with air quality modelling. The spatial representativeness of background rural monitoring stations has been assessed through relating CHIMERE chemistry-transport (v2013) model simulations at 5 x 5 km² resolution and measured data at the stations in Spain (including the Canary Islands) for the years 2019-2023 considering NO₂, SO₂, O₃, PM₁₀ and atmospheric deposition. With this analysis, the suitability of current monitoring stations to represent the air quality in National Parks is being assessed. A risk analysis of the effects on terrestrial ecosystems using CLRTAP critical levels and loads is being performed using the CHIMERE model in the different National Parks. Additionally, a new air quality and deposition monitoring programme has been initiated in 2025 in all the National Parks to measure NO₂, SO₂, O₃ and NH₃ using passive samplers and atmospheric wet deposition using bulk collectors connected to ion-exchange resins. Local monitoring data will be used to determine the spatial variability of air quality and deposition within the National Parks and will be compared with modelled data. Effects on aquatic ecosystems are being assessed applying the methodology of CLRTAP ICP-Waters in all the National Parks with suitable locations, including the Canary Islands. Preliminary results will be presented discussing representativeness of current monitoring stations, monitoring techniques available in remote locations and the modelling analyses required.

Keywords

nitrogen deposition, air pollution, Mediterranean ecosystems, monitoring, modelling

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.